

Solving 0-1 Knapsack Problem with variants of Genetic Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

The 0-1 knapsack problem is a NP-complete classical combinatorial optimization problem (COP). It is a challenging task to find optimal solution for large size problem instances. In this study, four types of mutation operation have been incorporated in Genetic Algorithm (GA) for solving 0-1 knapsack problem. The four variants are GA with bit flip mutation (FGA), GA with swap mutation (SGA), GA with insertion mutation (IGA) and GA with inversion mutation (IVGA). A modified penalty function (MPF) is used to calculate fitness of chromosome and eliminate infeasible chromosome from the population. The proposed algorithms are tested with certain 0-1 knapsack problem instances available in literature. Under the same preconditions, numerical result shows the superiority of the proposed FGA over other algorithms.

KEYWORDS: COP, Genetic Algorithm (GA), 0-1 knapsack problem, MPF, NP-complete.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Knapsack problem is a well-known discrete combinatorial optimization problem where the profit has to be maximized in a knapsack within its capacity (Dantzig, 1957). In the literature many applications of knapsack problem like resource allocation (Li et al., 2015), decision support (Fielder et al., 2016) and project selection (Bichler et al., 2018) have been presented. It can be classified into 0-1 knapsack problem (KP01), bounded knapsack problem, multiple choice knapsack problem, and multidimensional knapsack problem (Bansal et al., 2012). Among the knapsack problem family, the KP01 is popular and widely studied example of an NP-hard combinatorial optimization problem (COP). In a 0-1 knapsack problem, there is a set of items with fixed weight and respective profit value. The main objective is to maximize the profit value by selecting best suitable items within the knapsack capacity. Each item can be selected only once. In this problem, item from the list is either selected fully or not selected at all. A set of 'n' items, each with weight W_i , profit P_i and knapsack capacity as 'M' are given. Mathematically, 0-1 knapsack problem can be defined as follows:

Maximize: $\sum P_i X_i$ for i from 1 to n

Subject to $\sum W_i X_i \leq M$ and $X_i = 0$ or 1

Where X_i represents a decision variable. If X_i is 1, i^{th} item will be selected. Otherwise, i^{th} item will be rejected.

The 0-1 knapsack problem has been widely studied in the last few decades (Sundarkar et al., 2021), (Mandal et al., 2024). Different approaches have been proposed to solve KP01, which can be classified into two categories: deterministic algorithms and metaheuristic algorithms. Branch and bound algorithm (B&B) and dynamic programming are the typical deterministic algorithms for solving KP01. Deterministic algorithms perform well on the small size problem instance. But deterministic algorithms are not suitable for optimizing large scale KP01. On the other hand, metaheuristic optimization algorithm is a kind of stochastic algorithm which can accelerate the optimization process and find solutions in reasonable time but not guaranteeing to find the optimal solution.

The genetic algorithm (GA) and its variants were pioneered and developed in the 1960s by John Holland, his students, and colleagues (McCall., 2005). The GA is a population-based metaheuristic algorithm that mimics the genetic structure and behaviour of chromosomes. In GA, the selection, crossover, mutation and recombination are used in the field of optimization algorithm for the first time. Crossover and mutation operations can improve the diversity of solutions in GA. So, genetic operators have often been adopted by binary algorithms for solving 0-1 knapsack problems.

In this paper, four variants of genetic algorithm like FGA, SGA, IGA and IVGA are proposed for solving KP01.

Section 2 describes the details of the genetic algorithm. In Section 3 implementation of proposed variations of genetic algorithm is discussed. Experimental results and discussion on the proposed algorithm are reported in section 4. Final conclusions are given in conclusion section.

2 GENETIC ALGORITHM

The GA is a population-based metaheuristic algorithm that mimics the genetic structure and behaviour of chromosomes. It begins with a set of candidate solutions (chromosomes) called population. The basic components of the GA are chromosome encoding, fitness calculation, selection, crossover and mutation scheme. For example, consider a chromosome is 1 1 0 0 1. The value '1' indicates that the corresponding item is selected and '0' indicates that the corresponding item is rejected.

2.1 Fitness Function

Fitness of chromosomes are calculated and eliminated infeasible chromosomes by MPF (Mandal et al., 2024). It is shown by Eqs. (1) as follows

$$f(c) = \text{Max}(\sum P_i X_i + \text{Min}(0, \eta(\mu - \sum W_i X_i)), 0) \text{ for } i \text{ from } 1 \text{ to } n. \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Where } \eta = 2(\sum W_i X_i) \text{ and } \mu \text{ is capacity constraint}$$

2.2 Selection

The selection process is based on fitness of chromosome. Chromosomes that are evaluated with higher fitness values will most likely be selected to reproduce, whereas, those with low values will be discarded. The fittest chromosomes may be selected several times for mating population. There are different types of selection methods, such as Roulette-Wheel selection, Tournament Selection and Stochastic selection.

2.3 Crossover

It is analogous to biological reproduction. In this study, chromosomes are selected using Roulette-wheel selection operator and crossover sites are chosen randomly. Then the genes are exchanged at these crossover sites. Thus, two completely new chromosomes (offsprings) are produced for the next generation that inherit traits of both parents. For example, consider the following parent chromosomes and a crossover point at position 4. After crossover two offsprings are produced as shown below.

Parent 1 : 1 0 0 1 0 1	offspring 1 : 1 0 0 1 0 0
Parent 2 : 1 1 1 0 0 0	offspring 2 : 1 1 1 0 0 1

2.4 Mutation

Mutation is analogous to biological mutation. Mutation operators are key for maintaining genetic diversity within the population, allowing exploration of the search space. The key idea is to insert random genes in chromosome to maintain the genetic diversity within the population of genetic algorithm to avoid premature convergence. Hence, four types of mutation like bit flipping, swap, insertion and inversion have been used.

- Bit flip mutation operator flips the value of a randomly chosen gene in the chromosome, changing from 1 to 0 or from 0 to 1. For example, suppose a chromosome is: 10010. Flip the gene at position 5. The offspring is 10011.

- Swap mutation involves swapping the positions of two randomly chosen genes in a chromosome. For example, suppose a chromosome is:10010. Swap the genes at position 2 and 4. The offspring is 11000.
- Insertion mutation involves removing one gene from its position in a chromosome and inserting it at another position within the chromosome. For example, suppose a chromosome is:10010. Remove the gene at position 2 and insert at 4. The offspring is 10100.
- Inversion mutation involves reversing the order of a subset of genes within a chromosome. For example, suppose a chromosome is:10010. Invert the segment between 2 and 4. The offspring is 11000.

3 IMPLEMENTATION OF PROPOSED VARIATIONS OF GENETIC ALGORITHM (GA)

In this section variations of GA are presented to solve the 0-1 knapsack problem. The following steps will clarify the main concepts in the proposed genetic algorithm with bit flip mutation (FGA).

Step1 Population initialization: Initial population are generated and other control variables such as population size, maximum number of iterations are specified.

Step2 Fitness calculation: Fitness of each chromosome is calculated by Eqs. (1).

Step3 Selection: Fittest chromosomes are selected through the Roulette-Wheel selection for mating population.

Step4 Crossover: Single point crossover operator combines two parent chromosomes to produce offspring.

Step5 Mutation: Bit flip mutation is used to produce offspring.

Step6 Stopping criterion: Hence, Step 3, 4, 5 and survivors' selection for next generation are repeated until the end condition is satisfied. Here, a fixed number of generations is used as end condition. If the generation of the proposed algorithm reaches at this fixed value, it will be stopped and best solution will be printed.

In SGA, the only swap mutation is done after crossover operation.

In IGA, the only insertion mutation is done after crossover operation.

In IVGA, the only inversion mutation is done after crossover operation.

Flowchart of genetic algorithm is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of genetic algorithm.

4 EXPERIMENT RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, dataset details and experimental results are given. The overall performance of the proposed algorithms is examined by using 10 (ten) benchmark 0-1 knapsack problem instances. The set of 0-1 knapsack instances (kp-1 to kp-10) are taken from (Sundarkar et al., 2021). The set of ten small scale 0-1 knapsack problem instances are listed in Table 1. The proposed algorithms are executed 20 times individually for each instance.

The algorithms are coded in Python 3.9 with Pycharm IDE and experiments are carried out using a Intel Core (TM) i7-5500U CPU @ 2.40GHz, 8GB RAM and operating system is Windows 10.

Table 1. Small scale 0-1 knapsack problem instances (Sundarkar et al.,2021).

Instance	Item	Capacit	Weight (W_i) of each item	Profit (P_i) of each item
kp-1	10	269	95, 4, 60, 32, 23, 72, 80, 62, 65, 46	55, 10, 47, 5, 4, 50, 8, 61, 85, 87
kp-2	20	878	92, 4, 43, 83, 84, 68, 92, 82, 6, 44, 32, 18, 56, 83, 25, 96, 70, 48, 14, 58	44, 46, 90, 72, 91, 40, 75, 35, 8, 54, 78, 40, 77, 15, 61, 17, 75, 29, 75, 63
kp-3	4	20	6, 5, 9, 7	9, 11, 13, 15
kp-4	4	11	2, 4, 6, 7	6, 10, 12, 13
kp-5	15	375	56.358531, 80.87405, 47.987304, 89.59624, 74.660482, 85.894345, 51.353496, 1.498459, 36.445204, 16.589862, 44.569231, 0.466933, 37.788018, 57.118442, 60.716575	0.125126, 19.330424, 58.500931, 35.029145, 82.284005, 17.41081, 71.050142, 30.399487, 9.140294, 14.731285, 98.852504, 11.908322, 0.89114, 53.166295, 60.176397
kp-6	10	60	30, 25, 20, 18, 17, 11, 5, 2, 1, 1	20, 18, 17, 15, 15, 10, 5, 3, 1, 1
kp-7	7	50	31, 10, 20, 19, 4, 3, 6	70, 20, 39, 37, 7, 5, 10
kp-8	23	10000	983, 982, 981, 980, 979, 978, 488, 976, 972, 486, 486, 972, 972, 485, 485, 969, 966, 483, 964, 963, 961, 958, 959	81, 980, 979, 978, 977, 976, 487, 974, 970, 485, 485, 970, 970, 484, 484, 976, 974, 482, 962, 961, 959, 958, 857
kp-9	5	80	15, 20, 17, 8, 31	33, 24, 36, 37, 12
kp-10	20	879	84, 83, 43, 4, 44, 6, 82, 92, 25, 83, 56, 18, 58, 14, 48, 70, 96, 32, 68, 92	91, 72, 90, 46, 55, 8, 35, 75, 61, 15, 77, 40, 63, 75, 29, 75, 17, 78, 40, 44

Parameters of proposed algorithm are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Parameters of proposed algorithms.

FGA	SGA	IGA	IVGA
Population size: 2 * Items Fixed iteration: 300 Selection: Roulette-Wheel Crossover: Single Point (Random Selected) Mutation: Flip Mutation Probability: 1/Items	Population size: 2 * Items Fixed iteration: 300 Selection: Roulette-Wheel Crossover: Single Point (Random Selected) Mutation: Swap Mutation Probability: 1/Items	Population size: 2 * Items Fixed iteration: 300 Selection: Roulette-Wheel Crossover: Single Point (Random Selected) Mutation: Insertion Mutation Probability: 1/Items	Population size: 2 * Items Fixed iteration: 300 Selection: Roulette-Wheel Crossover: Single Point (Random Selected) Mutation: Inversion Mutation Probability: 1/Items

The results obtained are shown in table 3 and the success rate in table 4. It is observed that the proposed algorithms give the optimal solutions for all instances except kp-8 instance.

Table 3. Optimal result obtained from the proposed algorithms.

Instance	No. of item	Optimum Profit	FGA	SGA	IGA	IVGA
kp-1	10	295	295	295	295	295
kp-2	20	1024	1024	1024	1024	1024

kp-3	4	35	35	35	35	35
kp-4	4	23	23	23	23	23
kp-5	15	481.069	481.069	481.069	481.069	481.069
kp-6	10	52	52	52	52	52
kp-7	7	107	107	107	107	107
kp-8	23	9767	9756	9756	9756	9756
kp-9	5	130	130	130	130	130
Kp-10	20	1025	1025	1025	1025	1025

Table 4. Success rate of proposed algorithms for kp-1 to kp-10.

Instance	No. of item	Optimum Profit	FGA	SGA	IGA	IVGA
kp-1	10	295	95	50	60	60
kp-2	20	1024	100	95	30	55
kp-3	4	35	100	100	100	100
kp-4	4	23	100	100	100	100
kp-5	15	481.069	90	55	30	45
kp-6	10	52	100	80	100	90
kp-7	7	107	95	70	60	55
kp-8	23	9767	0	0	0	0
kp-9	5	130	100	100	100	100
Kp-10	20	1025	100	95	80	85

The comparative convergence graph obtained from the proposed algorithm for kp-10 is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Comparative convergence graph for kp-10 instance.

The visualized version of Table 4 is presented in Figure 3. Looking at Table 4 and Figure 3 the FGA is best performer.

Figure 3. Comparative graph for success rate.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In literature, large number of applications of 0-1 knapsack problem are presented. Different metaheuristic algorithms are investigated to optimize the solutions. This paper presents four variations of genetic algorithm to solve the 0-1 knapsack problem. These are optimization algorithms encouraged by behaviour of chromosomes. Performance of proposed algorithm decreased with increase in problem size which leads to increase in search space and number of combinations. There is a scope of improvement in the variations that would provide optimal results even for large instances.

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